
TOWARDS OPC UA OVER SHARED MEMORY AS AN OPEN INTRA-HOST MIDDLEWARE FOR AUTOMATION SOFTWARE

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ABSTRACT

The increasing virtualization of automation software and its decoupling from hardware introduces a significant change in industrial automation. This transition allows classical operational technology software instances, such as programmable logic controllers, to coexist on the same host system alongside applications from various domains. Such coexistence offers substantial potential for a more efficient interconnection between applications from different areas, overcoming typical limitations associated with conventional interfaces. However, current middleware solutions for automation applications are often proprietary and not standardized. In this paper, we present an initial concept for an intra-host middleware based on the OPC Unified Architecture, employing a centralized data directory combined with a shared-memory-based transport mechanism. The proposed concept aims to enable efficient, low-latency, and scalable communication, thereby facilitating seamless interaction between diverse automation applications and promoting the use of microservice architectures.

Keywords OPC UA · Shared Memory · Interoperability · Virtualization · Microservices

1 Introduction

The demands placed on machinery in industrial production are continuously increasing, shifting from traditional mass production to more individualized products with smaller batch sizes and dynamic market requirements [1]. In order to meet these demands, machines and in particular their automation software, must become more flexible and cost-effective. This is essential to expand the economic viability of automation technology, especially for small and medium-sized enterprises where flexible and scalable automation solutions are becoming an important enabler for competitive manufacturing.

To meet these requirements, a fundamental transformation of automation software towards greater modularity, platform independence, and interoperability is needed, following principles established in modern information technology (IT) [2]. This is particularly relevant for cross-domain interoperability between operational technology (OT) systems and external software domains, as it enables and in some cases is a prerequisite for cost-efficient integration of modern approaches, such as software-defined and interconnected automation systems.

A key driver of this development is the increasing virtualization. Traditional automation instances, such as the runtime environment of a programmable logic controller (PLC), which were historically bound to dedicated control hardware, can now be executed on general-purpose operating systems. A common approach to achieve this is the use of containerization, which offers advantages such as improved portability, simplified deployment, and isolation between software instances. Consequently, automation applications can be run alongside software from other domains on a shared host system [3].

The resulting paradigm shift not only allows for more flexible deployment of automation solutions but also creates new potential for the integration and interconnection between heterogeneous software systems. A central component for such integration is an open and standardized middleware solution that enables high-performance and resource-efficient intra-host communication between individual software instances. Although some middleware and interface

solutions already exist for this purpose, they are usually vendor-specific and not standardized, limiting their use to closed, proprietary ecosystems. As a result, interoperability between different platforms is limited, which restricts the reusability and flexible deployment of software across various hardware systems.

To overcome these restrictions, the adoption of an open and standardized communication technology is essential. A prominent candidate in this context is OPC Unified Architecture (OPC UA). While OPC UA is primarily designed for network-based, host-to-host communication, its potential as a local middleware for software components on the same system has not yet been fully explored.

Against this background, this paper examines how the OPC UA standard can be used to enable resource-efficient, low-latency intra-host communication between modular software components in industrial automation. As an initial step, the scalability and data transparency of the OPC UA Client/Server model are analyzed. Based on these insights, a concept is proposed that addresses the identified challenges by combining a centralised data directory with shared memory as a transport mechanism, forming the foundation for a future prototype implementation.

2 Background and Related Work

The following section provides an overview of the current developments and relevant research in the fields of software virtualization, middleware technologies and OPC UA.

2.1 Virtualization in Industrial Automation

The virtualization of software and its influence on automation technology is receiving increasing attention in the literature.

Breivold et al. [3] describes emerging trends in automation technology and identifies the virtualization of software, in particular, as one of the key approaches to overcoming traditional challenges in industrial systems. A specific focus is placed on the ability to run different technologies on the same hardware. Through virtualization, real-time systems and non-time-critical applications, such as human-machine interfaces (HMI), can be operated separately and simultaneously on the same hardware. This creates flexibility and facilitates the gradual migration of legacy systems.

The authors of [4] provide a comprehensive analysis of the current state of research on the use of container-based virtualization in industrial real-time systems through a systematic literature review. Their work also highlights the growing use of container technologies in automation, particularly for the flexible deployment of control components. In this context, the necessity of communication frameworks in containerized microservice architectures is also discussed which, due to real-time requirements, must also exhibit deterministic behavior.

Tasci et al. [5] propose a container-based architecture for modular real-time control systems that utilizes messaging for communication and a hardware abstraction layer for greater flexibility. Benchmarks demonstrated suitable round-trip times for tightly synchronized distributed applications. The use of shared memory is emphasized as particularly performant, highlighting the importance of the communication mechanism for efficient intra-container data exchange.

While the benefits of virtualization and container-based deployments are well documented, the challenge of ensuring efficient and deterministic data exchange between co-located components is rarely addressed in detail.

2.2 Middleware as an Enabler for Modular and Scalable Automation Architectures

Middleware technologies play a pivotal role in shaping the architecture of distributed systems by enabling seamless communication and integration between heterogeneous software components. In the context of industrial automation, where the networking of digital units is rapidly increasing, middleware is an essential enabler for scalable and modular control solutions.

Ashiwai et al. [6] investigate the flexibility and decoupling of PLC software components, identifying loose coupling between software units as a key requirement for building modular and adaptable control systems. To achieve this, the authors propose a middleware approach in the form of a 'PLC Service Bus', designed for use within the IEC 61499 standard. The architecture aims to replace global variables commonly associated with hidden dependencies in PLC software, by introducing a service-oriented communication model that promotes clearer interfaces and greater system modularity.

Sommer et al. [7] examines the communication requirements of industrial production systems within the context of the Industrial Internet of Things (IIoT), focusing on the use of message-oriented middleware (MOM) to enable distributed and loosely coupled automation architectures. Key challenges identified include the decoupling of communication

partners, scalability in increasingly complex systems, and efficiency in terms of latency and throughput. The authors highlight the importance of middleware solutions being easily integrable, fault-tolerant, and adaptable to diverse application scenarios. The paper also suggests a methodology for choosing suitable middleware implementations based on qualitative and quantitative criteria, focusing on transport-layer communication, without distinguishing between intra-host and host-to-host interactions.

Pöhl et al. [8] present the open-source middleware Eclipse iceoryx, which is based on a shared memory transport mechanism and was originally developed for safety-critical intra-host communication in the automotive industry. The middleware is specifically designed for high efficiency and reliability, making it particularly well-suited for systems with real-time requirements. A key feature is its zero-copy principle, which allows data to be transferred between sender and receiver without additional copying. This not only minimizes latency but also decouples the data transmission time from the size of the payload. The authors demonstrate that iceoryx achieves performance comparable to monolithic systems while enabling strong decoupling between software components, an essential feature of modern, modular automation solutions.

Although the listed literature emphasize modularity and decoupling, the integration of standardized semantic meta models, such as defined by OPC UA, has received limited attention in this context.

2.3 OPC UA

OPC UA is a platform- and vendor-independent communication standard that, due to its integrated security mechanisms and data modeling capabilities, is regarded as one of the key communication technologies for industrial automation in the context of Industry 4.0. [9]

For communication, OPC UA provides two fundamental models: the Client/Server model and the Publish/Subscribe (PubSub) model. The Client/Server model is based on a passive server that organizes data within the so called Address Space and offers standardized services through which clients can interact with the server [10]. In contrast, the more recent PubSub model was designed to support scalable and resource-efficient transmission of high-frequency data and serves as a complement to the request-based Client/Server model [11]. This extension expands the applicability of OPC UA, particularly for time-sensitive applications [12].

In the literature, a wide range of OPC UA use cases can be found. In [9], OPC UA is employed for machine data monitoring and the flexible orchestration of cyber-physical production systems. Similarly, Girbea et al. [13] utilize OPC UA to enable service-oriented and unified control of industrial production systems, including their semantic description. In [14], OPC UA serves as the central communication layer within a distributed control architecture for industrial robots.

The listed examples illustrate that OPC UA is widely used as an interface for the integration and semantic modeling of physical assets within distributed system architectures, mainly due to its openness and extensive industrial support.

In this context, Großmann et al. [15] address the growing number of distributed OPC UA servers in industrial environments and the challenges regarding transparency and system management. The authors propose an aggregation server which accesses multiple servers and consolidates their information to reduce connection complexity for higher-level systems.

While much of the current literature focuses on distributed, inter-host communication scenarios, the use of OPC UA as a middleware within a single host between modular software instances received limited attention in the existing literature.

3 Contribution

In this chapter, we present a first concept for the use of OPC UA as an intra-host middleware. The concept focuses initially on the Client/Server model and considers basic OPC UA services, such as reading, writing and browsing.

The rest of this section is structured as follows: first, we outline the key requirements for an intra-host middleware in the context of modular automation systems. We then examine the limitations of using OPC UA Client/Server in scaling distributed software architectures. Finally, we propose an alternative approach to overcome the identified limitations and discuss the use of shared memory as transport mechanism.

3.1 Key Requirements

In order to realise the idea, three main requirements were defined derived from the needs of industrial automation and the middleware demands of distributed software architectures.

3.1.1 Security and Safety

Since automation systems are deployed in production-critical and often safety-relevant domains, secure and safe data communication is of paramount importance in industrial environments. Faulty or manipulated data can not only cause production downtime but also endanger human lives or machinery. For this reason, the security of the transmitted data as well as robust communication in the spirit of the OPC UA standard must be taken into account.

3.1.2 Performance and Efficiency

High performance is essential to ensure that the proposed approach can be reliably applied even in demanding use cases with low latency requirements and high message throughput. At the same time, efficient resource utilisation is crucial in order to maintain system stability under high communication loads and to support usage on devices with limited computing and memory resources.

3.1.3 Scalability

To remain functional as the number of communication participants and data sources increases, scalable data orchestration and efficient management of communication relationships must be ensured. This ensures operability even in large and dynamic software environments.

3.2 Scalability Challenges in Distributed Software Architectures with OPC UA

The use of the OPC UA Client/Server model in distributed systems, such as microservice architectures, presents several challenges as scalability increases. When each application in such a system implements both an OPC UA server and client interface to provide (producer) and consume (consumer) data, a self-organizing peer-to-peer architecture emerges in which all participants communicate with each other bidirectionally, Fig. 1.

Figure 1: Client Server Connections Between Multiple Applications

Although direct data exchange between applications can be efficient, this approach leads to increasing complexity as the number of communication participants grows. Each application must maintain dedicated client instances for each data source, which increases the administrative and communication overheads. While the OPC UA Publish/Subscribe model addresses these scalability issues, it does not provide request-response interactions, which remain essential in service-oriented automation environments.

Furthermore, the lack of a centralised overview of all available data leads to additional overheads. Each application must search relevant OPC UA servers independently to discover accessible data. This increases communication load and reduces transparency regarding data availability.

3.3 A Central Server as Data Directory and Broker

To address the challenges mentioned above, a centrally organized architecture with a dedicated OPC UA server is proposed. This server acts as a data directory and intermediary, by listing all available data and their respective sources within its address space. Unlike an aggregation server, which actively connects to data sources, providers in this architecture must register their data with the directory server as clients.

When a consumer wants to access specific data, the directory server forwards the request to the appropriate producer. The producer processes the request through its server interface and returns the data to the consumer, Fig. 2.

This approach aims to ensure transparency of the data available within the system, even as it scales, while avoiding time- and resource-intensive browsing operations. Moreover, each application only needs to establish and maintain a single

client connection to the directory server, which reduces the complexity of data access as the number of participants grows.

Figure 2: Central Server as Data Directory and Broker Interacting with Participants

Although the centralized architecture introduces a potential single point of failure, it simplifies coordination and data discovery, which is acceptable for an initial proof-of-concept. Future work may consider redundancy or decentralization to improve fault tolerance. The centralized approach also facilitates unified access control and interaction monitoring, even as the system scales.

3.4 Using Shared Memory as Communication Mechanism

In order to address the demands of high performance, reliability and efficiency a key design decision in our concept is the use of a shared memory as transport mechanism, instead of relying on conventional network-based transmission methods.

Shared memory is an inter-process communication (IPC) method where the operating system provides a memory segment that can be accessed by multiple processes concurrently [16]. Shared memory is supported by the standardized Portable Operating System Interface (POSIX), making it compatible with a wide range of operating systems, including Linux [17].

Compared to other intra-host mechanisms such as POSIX message queues or Unix domain sockets, shared memory offers the advantage that data does not need to be copied for exchange, as it can be accessed directly via its memory address. As a result, transmission speed is largely independent of payload size, which makes it particularly suitable for deterministic communication behavior. This also supports efficient scalability to multiple receivers, since each process can access the memory region directly without additional overhead. Despite the use of shared address spaces, the process-local memory of each application remains protected, preventing unauthorized access to private memory areas and minimizing security risks. [8]

However, using shared memory as a communication mechanism in a distributed software architecture requires explicit coordination of access to the memory segments [8]. Ensuring safe and reliable usage of this IPC mechanism is a significant challenge that involves preventing race conditions, deadlocks, unauthorized access, and data corruption due to process crashes [8]. To address these challenges, a dedicated shared memory framework will be employed.

As the interaction patterns with the shared memory depend on the design of the high-level API provided by a specific framework, implementation details will be specified during the ongoing development, once a concrete framework has been selected. Since security considerations are also closely linked to the framework’s capabilities, they will be addressed in more depth at a later stage. In the meantime, basic access control via OS-level permissions via Linux user groups is assumed to provide a first layer of protection.

4 Conclusion and Future Work

This paper presents an initial concept for an intra-host middleware that utilizes OPC UA in combination with a shared memory transport mechanism to enable low latency, scalable, and efficient communication between automation applications running on the same host system. By introducing a centralized server that acts as a global data directory and intermediary between communication participants, the proposed architecture addresses the identified challenges of direct client-server communication in growing distributed software systems.

In the next step, a suitable shared memory framework will be selected as the foundation for a prototype implementation. Possible hurdles such as limited support for complex or dynamic data structures, or missing features required to realize key OPC UA mechanisms, must be considered during this phase. Security and real-time aspects, while relevant for industrial use, will be addressed in later phases of the project due to their complexity.

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